

Some Important Aspects of the NFDI4Cat Ontology and Metadata Design

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NFDI for Catalysis-Related Sciences

Project structure and management

TA1: Ontology Development and Metadata Standards

TA5: Dissemination and Outreach/ Training

TA2: Data standards, Data Collection, Interfaces

TA6: Networking with NFDIs, SFBs and International

TA3: Data Analysis and Re-Use, Quality Management

TA7: IP and Confidentiality, Licences and Reward models

TA4: Linked Extensible Infrastructure and Access Management

TA8: Management

Data & Metadata Standards

Data Science & Information Infrastructure Design

Community & User-related Aspects

Linked Data Principles

1. Use URIs as names for things
2. Use HTTP URIs so that people can look up those names
3. When someone looks up a URI, provide useful RDF information
4. Include RDF statements that link to other URIs so that they can discover related things

Tim Berners-Lee 2007
<http://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

Linked Data Principles

Within NFDI URIs will be user for:

- Data
- Chemical substances
- Samples
- Devices
- Processes
- Domain-specific relations
-

Challenges

- Overall structure of metadata
- Structure and assignment of URIs
- Representation of complex and diverse workflows
- Tedious collection of metadata
- User-invariance of collected metadata
- Designing subsumption relations in ontology
- Determining whether to design an item as a class or property
- Designing complex relations

Ideal NFDI4Cat Ontology

- metadata-oriented
- suitable for a clear representation of the research workflow and all resources involved
- the classes and relations include all relevant semantic search terms
- suitable for semantic query according to workflow patterns
- uniquely shape an interactive metadata inquiry by appropriate software
- allows the metadata inquiry and collection software to be only loosely coupled with the context of metadata

Metadata Model

The metadata related to an instance of class A are given by its properties. This would imply that in the case of an object property relating classes A and B, there is also a need for providing the metadata for the instance of class B, and so forth.

- Inheritance
- Modularity: all expansions are independent

Polymorphism

A general pathway for a semiautomatic construction of metadata

The range of properties representing the metadata within a domain-specific model should be represented using the most general class, while only the most specific classes should be used to instantiate metadata.

Toluene Hydrodealkylation Process

Metadata4Ing

```
#
# Metadata prototype for toluene hydrodealkylation process
#
@prefix ms: <http://www.nfdi4cat.org/metaset_000001#> .
@prefix sm: <http://www.nfdi4cat.org/substance_manufacturers#> .
@prefix dev: <http://www.nfdi4cat.org/tud/devices#> .
@prefix o4cat: <http://www.nfdi.org/nfdi4cat/ontochem#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> .

# Specification of the current research step
ms:ResearchStep_1 a o4cat:ResearchStep.
ms:ResearchStep_1 o4cat:hasNProcessingModules 14 .
ms:ResearchStep_1 o4cat:hasProcessingModule ms:ProcessingModule_1 ,
ms:ProcessingModule_2 ,
ms:ProcessingModule_3 ,
.....
ms:ProcessingModule_14 .
```


Scheme for Metadata Inquiry


```

ms:ResearchStep_1      a o4cat:ResearchStep.
ms:ResearchStep_1      o4cat:hasNProcessingModules 14 .
.....
ms:ResearchStep_1      o4cat:hasProcessingModule      ms:ProcessingModule_5 .
ms:ProcessingModule_5  a      o4cat:UnitOperationModule
  
```

Scheme for Metadata Inquiry

ms:ProcessingModule_5	o4cat:hasUnitOperation	ms:Mixing_1.
ms:Mixing_1	a	o4cat:UOMixingMagnetic
	o4cat:mixingDevice	dev:Reactor_xxx
	o4cat:mixingMagneticRate	200

Metadata

```
.....
# Processing module #5
ms:ProcessingModule_5    a
    o4cat:hasProcessingTask      o4cat:PhysChemProcessingModule;
    o4cat:hasChemicalReaction    o4cat:CHEMICAL_REACTION;
    o4cat:hasProcessingDevice     ms:Reaction_1;
    o4cat:hasUnitOperation        dev:Reactor_xxx;
    o4cat:hasUnitOperation        ms:Mixing_1;
    o4cat:referenceLabel          ms:Heating_1;
    rdfs:label                    "Benzene production" ;
    o4cat:hasChemicalMaterialInput "C7H8 + H2 -> C6H6 + CH4 conversion" ;
    o4cat:hasChemicalMaterialOutput ms:Substance_1, ms:Substance_2;
    ms:Reaction_1              a
    o4cat:chemicalReactionReagent ms:Substance_1, ms:Substance_2;
    o4cat:chemicalReactionProduct ms:Substance_3, ms:Substance_4;
    o4cat:hasReactionMixture      ms:Mixture_1;
    o4cat:isReactionProved         1 .
    ms:Mixture_1                  a
    o4cat:hasChemicalComponent     ms:Substance_1, ms:Substance_2, ms:Substance_3, ms:Substance_4 .
    ms:Mixing_1                    a
    o4cat:mixingDevice              o4cat:UOMixingMagnetic;
    o4cat:mixingMagneticRate        dev:Reactor_xxx ;
    ms:Heating_1                   200.
    o4cat:heatingMethod             o4cat:UOHeating;
    o4cat:heatingTemperature        o4cat:HEATING_THERMOBATH;
    ms:Substance_3                  300. # in kelvin units
    o4cat:referenceLabel            o4cat:ChemicalCompound;
    o4cat:inChIKey                  "Benzene";
    o4cat:inChIKey                  "YXFVVABEGXRONW-UHFFFAOYSA-N". # IUPAC Standard InChIKey
.....
```

Disclaimer.

No human brain is harmed by collecting RDF metadata. All tedious manipulations are performed programmatically in a semi-automatic fashion by applying an informal metadata inquiry shaped by the appropriate ontology.

- Metaset is a collection of the RDF graph statements representing the metadata for a given (publishable) research step
- Each metaset has its own URI
- It can be serialized into a file(s) or triple store
- Principal composition of the URI of a metaset:

<http://www.instituteXXX/groupYYY/metasetNNN>

- URI of a metaset:

<http://www.instituteXXX/groupYYY/metasetNNN>

- URI of a resource first provided in the associated study :

http://www.instituteXXX/groupYYY/metasetNNN#ClassName_M = ms:ClassName_M

- Straightforward automatic URI scheme for a detailed documentation of a resource's provenance
- Efficient indexing
- Straightforward navigation between metaset by referring e.g. a resource ms_1 :name in metaset ms_2

THANK YOU!